

Applying the Shockley diode equation to model the current-voltage characteristics of singular wavelength LEDs (400-700nm)

Research question: How accurately can the Shockley diode equation be used to model the current-voltage characteristics of singular wavelength LEDs (400-700nm)?
Simulation: DCACLab (Online Circuit Simulator)

Introduction:

Nowadays the world is witnessing increased applications and development of LED's. In purchasing a new TV it occurred to me that LEDs are the leading technology in the market; perhaps one has heard of QLED (Quantum dot LED) TVs and as of recent OLED (Organic LED) TVs, which as their names signify are both made special due to their perplexing LED technologies. Fundamentally speaking; LEDs or light emitting diodes are semiconductor devices that emit light of singular wavelengths upon flow of current. Having grown fascinated by LEDs' ability to emit light of virtually any wavelength (spanning the entirety of the visible spectrum: 400 ~ 700nm) (Banerjee & Chattopadhyay, 2018) I speculated if each discrete wavelength emitting LED possessed a unique set of IV characteristics. Eager to explore the workings of LEDs I stumbled upon the Shockley diode equation; an equation invented by the celebrated American physicist and inventor William Shockley which relates current to applied forward bias for a semiconductor diode (Jones, 2014); this led to my research question "**How accurately can the Shockley diode equation be used to model the current-voltage characteristics of singular wavelength LEDs (400-700nm)?**".

Background Information:

Simply put, a diode is a two terminal electrical component that essentially acts as a valve such that it allows the flow of current in one direction and prevents current flow in the other. (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 1998) Thus, an ideal diode is said to have 0 resistance in the forward direction and infinite resistance in the reverse direction. The most common type of diodes are semiconductor diodes which are characterized by operating under a low voltage direct current. Given low voltage direct current and the connection of the diode in the forward direction the diode conducts current and is said to be 'forward biased'. If the diode is reversed such that the diode is connected in the reverse direction, the diode blocks current flow and is said to be 'reverse biased'.

The most common semiconductor diode is a PN junction diode. A PN junction diode is created by joining a n-type semiconductor (a material with an overriding number of free electrons and an infinitesimal number of holes) and a p-type semiconductor (a material with an overriding number of holes and an infinitesimal number of free electrons). Fundamentally, holes are "places depleted of electrons that act as positively charged particles" (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 1998). It is imperative to highlight that in n-type semiconductors free electrons act as the majority charge carriers meanwhile, in p-type semiconductors holes act as the majority charge carriers. At the junction of both semiconductors, free electrons in the n-type semiconductor combine with holes in the p-type semiconductor which give rise to uncovered negative ions in the p-type semiconductor and vice versa giving rise to uncovered positive ions

in the n-type semiconductor. Thus, the uncovered ions form a region known as the ‘depletion region’ whereby all charge carriers in the region have been depleted. Due to the presence of uncovered positive and negative ions, an electric field is created which halts the migration of any charge carriers within this region. This electric field is termed the “barrier potential” (Electrical4U, 2021).

Figure 1: Diode mechanism (BYJU'S, 2020)

Additionally, one must pay attention to the anode and cathode; simply put, the anode is the terminal connected to the p-type side of the diode conversely, the cathode is the terminal connected to the n-type side of the diode. We are now in a better position to redefine the forward biased and reverse biased states of a diode. A diode is said to be forward biased if the positive terminal of the voltage source is connected to the p-type side and the negative terminal of the voltage source is connected to the n-type side and vice versa for a reverse biased diode (BYJU'S, 2020). Thus, it can be discerned that a diode schematic diagram as shown below illustrates the forward biased condition of a diode whereby the arrowhead points in the conventional direction of current which implies positive to negative flow of current hence it is further implied that the positive terminal is connected to the p-type side (+ anode) and the negative terminal is connected to the n-type side (- cathode) (Electrical4U, 2021). **The remainder of this exploration will assume forward biased state.**

Figure 2 Diode schematic (Electrical4U, 2021)

With regards to LEDs, LEDs or light emitting diodes are a unique type of PN junction diode made of distinctive semiconductor compounds; some common examples include Gallium Phosphide (GaP) and Gallium Arsenide Phosphide (GaAsP). It is essential to note that LEDs only emit light in the forward biased state given low voltage direct current. Furthermore, the emission of light in LEDs takes place by means of electroluminescence. Electroluminescence is a phenomenon by which photons of different wavelengths are emitted as a result of radiative recombination (Zarrintaj, Vahabi, Saeb, & Masous, 2019). Radiative recombination occurs when an electron recombines with a hole and the excess energy that results is emitted in the form of photons. The different photon wavelengths emitted are bounded by the LED's elemental composition where data has shown that no two elements have the same wavelengths in their spectrum (Tsokos, 2014), thus it can be discerned that each element/ semiconductor has defined energy bandgaps through

which the phenomenon of electroluminescence take place (Zarrintaj, Vahabi, Saeb, & Masous, 2019).

It is critical to take note of the following; typically, the current conducted by LEDs is measured in milliamperes (ma), moreover the typical rated forward current for a market standard LED is 12- 20ma (Electronics Tutorials, 2020), thus 20ma essentially serves as a rule of thumb. Accordingly, given a forward current of 20ma, the forward voltage will deliver maximum lumens/ luminous efficacy. **The forward biased voltage of an LED differs depending on the semiconductor material used and thus wavelength of light emitted** (Electronics Tutorials, 2020). Moreover, it is typically known that the shorter the wavelength the more voltage required such that the photon necessitates more energy for emission (bounded by the energy bandgap). In application a resistor is placed in series such that it acts as a current limiter as a typical voltage source will deliver intensified amounts of current (Electronics Tutorials, 2020). It is imperative to highlight that the variable that is forward voltage typically has a range whereby given the explicated 20ma (forward current), any voltage higher than the $V_f@20ma$ will cause the led to burn almost instantaneously, a voltage below the $V_f@20ma$ will not allow for maximal luminosity and a substantially low voltage won't permit the LED to conduct current.

Shockley diode equation:

The Shockley diode equation, alternatively known as the diode law was first published in William Shockley's "The Theory of p-n Junctions in Semiconductors and p-n Junction Transistors" and principally demonstrates the IV characteristics of a PN junction diode. The equation is displayed below:

$$I = I_S(e^{\frac{qV}{\eta kT}} - 1) \text{ (Shockley, 1949)}$$

Where, I is the diode current (A), I_S is the reverse bias saturation current (A); a critical factor which measures the recombination in a diode (PVEducation, n.d.) , q is the electron charge, V is the applied forward bias, k is Boltzmann's constant, T is the absolute temperature measured in kelvin and lastly η is the ideality factor/ emission coefficient which is effectively a measure of how closely the diode behaves with respect to an ideal diode ($\eta = 1$) thereby the η is habitually omitted in the case of an ideal diode.

While the Shockley diode equation is typically used to model the IV characteristics of a conventional diode, this exploration will exploit the equation in modelling the IV characteristics of LED's whereby LEDs are known to possess IV characteristics identical to those of diodes (Unacademy, n.d.). Moreover, it is critical to highlight that the parameters in which presumably distinguish a conventional diode from a LED and more precisely one wavelength of light to another is the ideality factor η as well as the reverse saturation current I_S .

The equation may be simplified such that for $v > 0.2V$ the -1 can be ignored (Engineering LibreTexts, 2021) thus the modified equation is:

$$I = I_S(e^{\frac{qV}{\eta kT}})$$

Taking the log of both sides allows for investigation of the explicated η and I_S :

$$\ln(I) = \ln(I_S) + \left(\frac{qV}{\eta kT}\right)V$$

Plotting the natural log of the current against the voltage yields a, a y-intercept $\ln(I_S)$, a **linear** slope $\frac{q}{\eta kT}$ and correspondingly a R-squared value **1**. The R-squared value/ coefficient of determination is a measure of the proportion of variance in the dependent variable ($\ln(I)$) that can be explained by changes in the independent variable (V). **Moreover, the R-squared value quantifies the extent of linear correlation between the 2 variables thus serves as a measure of accuracy whereby the scatter plot is ought to yield a linear slope of variable linearities.** Graphing $\ln(I_S)$ against V , ultimately allows for comparison of I_S and η across different wavelengths whereby q and K are constants and T is presumably controlled.

Hypothesis:

It is hypothesized that the Shockley diode equation can be utilized to model the IV characteristics of singular wavelength LEDs to a great extent such that graphing the natural log of the reverse bias saturation current against voltage yields a linear slope coupled with a high coefficient of determination across all wavelengths (0.9 to 1). My reasoning for said prediction is that similar to conventional diodes; LEDs are PN junction diodes; however, contrary to the standard silicon or germanium diodes, LEDs are comprised of several semiconductor compounds; nevertheless, upon research it has become palpable that the Shockley diode equation is equipped to make allowances for said variation through 2 critical factors: namely, the reverse saturation current and the ideality factor.

Variables:

Independent variables:

- 1- Wavelength of light emitting diode

In order to assess the potentiality of exploiting the Shockley diode equation in modelling the IV characteristics of LEDs, the equation will be applied to several wavelengths whereby each wavelength emitting LED is comprised of a unique set of semiconductors compounds. ‘The wavelengths are like fingerprints that can be used to identify the element’ thus allowing for comparison across LEDs’ slopes (solving for η) as well as y-intercepts (solving for I_S) as well as the afore explicated r squared value.

Below is a table extracted from dcaclab’s website illustrating the wavelengths made available by the simulation. The color names can be coordinated with the hyperlinked source to classify each colors wavelength. (Refer to appendix 1)

Figure 3 LED Color and its Corresponding Threshold Voltages (DCACLAB, 2018)

2- Forward bias voltage

As previously stipulated in the background information; each wavelength possess its own forward bias voltage, insinuating that the quantity cannot possibly be controlled across all wavelengths without either causing the LED to ‘burn out’ (assuming relatively high Vf) or forbidding the LED from conducting current in the first place (assuming substantially low Vf). Accordingly, a range has been experimentally defined for each LED through which the specified wavelength emitting LED delivers maximal lumens without ‘burning out’ (at max Vf) correspondingly at min Vf the LED conducts negligible current. The Vf has been incremented 5 times at a controlled increment (+0.1) across all wavelengths such that enough readings are to be gathered.

<u>Color/λ</u> <u>(nm)</u>	Ultra-red - 660	Super Orange - 612	Yellow - 585	Super lime green - 570	Aqua green - 525	Super blue - 470	Ultra-blue - 430
<u>Voltage</u>	1.3	1.7	1.6	1.5	2.8	2.9	3.1
	1.4	1.8	1.7	1.6	2.9	3.0	3.2
	1.5	1.9	1.8	1.7	3.0	3.1	3.3
	1.6	2.0	1.9	1.8	3.1	3.2	3.4
	1.7	2.1	2.0	1.9	3.2	3.3	3.5

Table 1 Forward voltage per wavelength

Dependent variable: Current conducted measured in amperes (A) using a multimeter.

Controlled variables:

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Reason for control</u>	<u>Method of control</u>
Resistance	<p>The resistance is directly proportional to the current thereby manipulating it would affect the current reading.</p> <p>Recall $V = IR$</p>	<p>The resistance will be controlled by using a resistor of 6 ohms which will be placed in series. 6 ohms was determined experimentally and allows for the current to be kept within the 20ma range across all wavelengths.</p>
Temperature	<p>To compare the ideality factor as well as the reverse saturation current across different wavelengths given $\ln(I) = \ln(I_S) + \left(\frac{qV}{\eta kT}\right)V$ the temperature must be controlled. In addition, temperature is known to be directly proportional to the internal resistance of the battery in addition to having negligible effects on the current reading of the LEDs.</p>	<p>The simulation assumes constant temperature which may be assumed to be 300 kelvin (26.85 °C); given 300 kelvin is the absolute room temperature.</p>

Apparatus:

- 1x Variable voltage source (Battery)
- 1x Multimeter (Ammeter, Setting: 3A)
- 1x Variable resistor (6 Ohms)
- 1x Customizable LED (Fwd V @20ma)
- 2x Wires

Circuit schematic:

Image of setup:

Procedure:

- 1- Head to dcaclab.com and proceed to the virtual lab.
- 2- To set up the schematic illustrated above, begin by inserting a battery from the overhead module (rotating it by 90 degrees).
- 3- Insert a resistor and fix its resistance at 6 ohms, do so by modifying the input method to ‘text’ and entering 6 ohms.
- 4- Insert a Led from the overhead module, once inserted click the gear icon and tick the ‘flip’ option such that the P-type side is connected to the anode terminal (+ anode).
- 5- Using wires, connect the Resistor and the LED in series with battery.
- 6- Insert an ideal ammeter and connect it in series (set the dial to 3A).
- 7- Now toggle the LED properties and select the desired color ex. Ultra-red (the colors’ names & wavelengths may be coordinated with the table present on the dcaclab website).
- 8- Begin by adjusting the battery voltage to the explicated minimum forward bias voltage in accordance with the wavelength being tested (ex. Ultra-red: 1.3 v).
- 9- Record the current reading.
- 10- Repeat steps 8-9 a total 5 times (incrementing the voltage a total of 5 times (min through max) ex. Ultra-red: 1.3, 1.4, 1.5, 1.6 & 1.7).
- 11- Repeat steps 7-10 a total of 7 times varying wavelength (Ultra Red, Super Orange, Yellow, Super lime green, Aqua green, super blue & Ultra blue).

Raw data:

No trials have been conducted due to the utilization of a simulation whereby trials would result in identical values. However, the voltage was incremented 5 times per wavelength such that more data points are available, allowing for a more representative/ accurate curve.

<u>Color/λ (nm)</u>	Ultra-red - 660		Super Orange - 612		Yellow - 585		Super lime green - 570		Aqua green - 525		Super blue - 470		Ultra-blue - 430	
	V	I	V	I	V	I	V	I	V	I	V	I	V	I
	1.3	0.00013	1.7	0.00062	1.6	0.00045	1.5	0.00031	2.8	0.00146	2.9	0.00173	3.1	0.00234
	1.4	0.00072	1.8	0.00232	1.7	0.00182	1.6	0.00139	2.9	0.00310	3.0	0.00379	3.2	0.00482
	1.5	0.00327	1.9	0.00679	1.8	0.00584	1.7	0.00493	3.0	0.00685	3.1	0.00757	3.3	0.00907
	1.6	0.00975	2.0	0.01468	1.9	0.01345	1.8	0.01222	3.1	0.01225	3.2	0.01348	3.4	0.01537
	1.7	0.01982	2.1	0.02520	2.0	0.02388	1.9	0.02255	3.2	0.02402	3.3	0.02148	3.5	0.02360

Table 3 Absolute uncertainties

Absolute uncertainty:

The absolute uncertainty of each variable was taken to be the smallest increment made available by the simulation; however, the wavelengths applied were a set of predetermined values which could not be toggled.

Wavelength	Voltage	Resistance	Current
N/A	$\pm 0.01V$	$\pm 1 \text{ ohm}$	$\pm 0.00001 \text{ A}$

Table 2 Absolute uncertainties

Processed data

- Using excel, the natural log of each respective current reading was taken. The values displayed below are exact and have not been rounded. Below are sample calculations for the min forward voltage of each wavelength. Refer to appendix for remaining values.

Color/ λ (nm)	Current (A) ± 0.00001	$\ln(I)$ (A)
Ultra-red - 660	0.00013	-8.9479761
Super Orange - 612	0.00062	-7.3857911
Yellow - 585	0.00045	-7.7062630
Super lime green - 570	0.00031	-8.0789383
Aqua green - 525	0.00146	-6.5293188
Super blue - 470	0.00173	-6.3596339
Ultra-blue - 430	0.00234	-6.0576043

Table 4 Sample processed data

- The raw data was graphed using a scatter plot resulting in a typical IV graph. Correspondingly, each curve was colored to aid in identification of the different wavelengths and their respective IV characteristics.

Graph 1 IV graph

- The natural log of the current was subsequently graphed against the voltage. Additionally, all curves were linearized whereby a line of best fit was added to each respective wavelength allowing for interpretation of the slopes as well as the y-intercepts. In addition, each r squared value was displayed.

Graph 2 $\ln(I)$ vs. V graph

4- The slope and y-intercept uncertainties were calculated:

Sample calculations: *ULTRA RED*

A table was created containing Voltage (the independent variable) and the natural log of the current (the dependent variable) and their respective absolute uncertainties. (The smallest and largest set of values were highlighted for use in the ensuing step).

Voltage (V) $\Delta V = \pm 0.01$	$\ln(I) \Delta = \pm 0.000000001$
1.3	-8.947976108
1.4	-7.236259346
1.5	-5.722965294
1.6	-4.630487994
1.7	-3.92106375

Table 5 V vs ln(I)

Next the maximum and minimum slope coordinates were calculated using the above highlighted max and min readings:

Maximum Slope		Minimum Slope	
$x+\Delta x$	$y-\Delta y$	$x-\Delta x$	$y+\Delta y$
1.31	-8.94797611	1.29	-8.947976107
1.69	-3.92106375	1.71	-3.921063751
$x-\Delta x$	$y+\Delta y$	$x+\Delta x$	$y-\Delta y$

The max and min coordinates were then plotted and their respective lines of best fit (the slope) equation as well as the R-squared values were displayed on the chart:

Graph 3 sample uncertainty graph

Finally, the Slope and Y-intercept uncertainties were calculated:

Slope Uncertainty: (Maximum Slope - Minimum Slope)/2

$$(13.229 - 11.969)/2 = \pm 0.665$$

Y-intercept Uncertainty: (Maximum Y-intercept - Minimum Y-intercept)/2

$$(-26.278 - -24.388)/2 = \pm -0.945$$

The above process has been repeated for each wavelength.

Wavelength	Slope uncertainty	Y-intercept uncertainty
Ultra-red - 660	± 0.665	± -0.945
Super Orange - 612	± 0.433795	± -0.882
Yellow - 585	± 0.49745	± -0.896
Super lime green - 570	± 0.573	± -0.9135
Aqua green - 525	± 0.35095	± -1.053
Super blue - 470	± 0.31565	± -0.9785
Ultra-blue - 430	± 0.63	± -0.9555

Table 6 Slope & Y-intercept uncertainties

- 5- Gather the slope and y-intercept readings and their representative uncertainties for each respective wavelength.

Color/ λ (nm)	Slope: $\frac{q}{\eta kT}$	Y-intercept: $\ln(I_s)$
Ultra-red - 660	12.66 ± 0.665	-25.081 ± -0.945
Super Orange - 612	9.2547 ± 0.433795	-22.853 ± -0.882
Yellow - 585	9.9432 ± 0.49745	-23.338 ± -0.896
Super lime green - 570	10.748 ± 0.573	-23.904 ± -0.9135
Aqua green - 525	6.975 ± 0.35095	-26.009 ± -1.053
Super blue - 470	6.3068 ± 0.31565	-24.544 ± -0.9785
Ultra-blue - 430	5.7818 ± 0.63	-23.883 ± -0.9555

Table 7 Slope & Y-intercept readings

- 6- The reverse saturation currents were calculated by taking the exponent of the $\ln(I_s)$ values; below is a sample calculation for Ultra red:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(I_s) &= -25.081 \\ I_s &= e^{-25.081} \\ I_s &= 1.280737422 \times 10^{-11} A \end{aligned}$$

The remaining wavelength reverse saturation currents were calculated using the excel equation function.

- 7- Assuming room temperature = 300 kelvin, the ideality factor for Ultra red was calculated as follows:

$$\frac{q}{\eta k T} = 12.66$$

Cross multiply:

$$q = 12.66 \times \eta k T$$

$$\frac{q}{12.66 \times k \times T} = \eta$$

Given:

$$q = 1.60 \times 10^{-19} \text{C}$$

$$k = 1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{JK}^{-1}$$

$$T = 300 \text{K}$$

$$\frac{1.60 \times 10^{-19}}{12.66 \times (1.38 \times 10^{-23}) \times (300)} = \eta$$

$$3.052712717 = \eta$$

The remaining wavelengths ideality factors were calculated using the excel equation function.

<u>Color/ λ (nm)</u>	η	I_s
Ultra-red - 660	3.05271272	1.28074E-11
Super Orange - 612	4.17596929	1.18869E-10
Yellow - 585	3.88681139	7.31872E-11
Super lime green - 570	3.59577065	4.15551E-11
Aqua green - 525	5.54083771	5.06331E-12
Super blue - 470	6.12788466	2.19117E-11
Ultra-blue - 430	6.68430990	4.24370E-11

Table 8 Ideality factors and reverse saturation currents

Conclusion:

Following intensive examination of LEDs' IV characteristics coupled with extensive manipulation of the Shockley diode equation across 7 singular wavelengths (ranging between 400-700nm), the following can be ascertained. In graphing the collected raw data, all wavelengths exhibited non-ohmic characteristics inferring that light emitting diodes do not obey ohms law ($I \propto V$) alternatively stated, voltage and current exhibit a nonlinear relationship (Refer to graph 1). With regards to the Shockley diode equation; graphing the natural log the of the current ($\ln(I)$) against the voltage (V) did not conduce a perfectly linear/ undeviating relationship ($r^2 = 1$) (refer to graph 2) nevertheless, the R-squared values attained ranged between a min of 0.9719 (Super Orange) and a max of 0.997 (Aqua Blue) which nonetheless indicates strong positive correlation across all wavelengths, implying that 97-99% of the proportion of variance in the dependent variable ($\ln(I)$) can be explained by changes in the independent variable (V). Alternatively stated, the model yielded slopes approaching $r^2 = 1$, thus indicating that LEDs are fit for the model in so asserting the validity of my hypothesis. It can thus be said that the Shockley diode equation accurately illustrates the IV characteristics of different wavelength LEDs whereby the model yielded relatively linear slopes coupled with R-squared values ranging between 0.9 and 1. Despite differing in semiconductor composition and consequently recombination measures, LED's remain diodes precisely PN junction diodes which share the

familiar functioning mechanism of conventional diodes thus justifying the analogous linearity. Moreover, it is critical to take note of the slope uncertainties in addition to the y-intercept uncertainties prior to explicating both quantities and their respective significance. The slope uncertainties ranged between ± 0.433795 (Super Orange) and ± 0.665 (Ultra Red) (refer to table 6/7) both which are relatively low, indicating that the slope ($\frac{q}{\eta kT}$) and thus the true value of η cannot vary significantly. As for the y-intercept uncertainties; the uncertainties lied between ± 0.882 and ± 0.9135 (refer to table 6/7) which affirmably is abnormal particularly since the y-intercept represents the $\ln(I_s)$, thus taking the exponent of the y-intercept (to attain I_s) would vary greatly bounded by such increment. Concerning the reverse saturation current (I_s), each wavelength possesses a one off value whereby each wavelength emitting LED possess unique recombination mechanisms, similarly each led possesses a singular ideality factor, ranging between 3.59577065 (super lime green) and 6.6843099 (Ultra-Blue) (refer to table 8), hence it can be ascertained that a super lime green LED most closely resembles an ideal diode ($\eta = 1$) however such disparity is made explainable by the applied voltage across the cell whereby the ideality factor varies with voltage. On a final note, the Shockley diode equation can thus be used to model the IV characteristics of LEDs differing in recombination and thus I_s and η bounded by the forward voltage range in which the equation accounts for.

Strengths:

This investigation possesses various strengths, namely the variation of wavelength 7 times which has allowed for more comparability in addition to affirming the hypothesized trend. Another strength is the accomplishment of this investigation’s purpose in a highly organized and facilitated manner such that the simulation expended highly resembled the hands-on experiment and perhaps granted more freedom in terms of altering both independent variables (the wavelengths and their relative forward bias voltages) in addition to granting a higher level of precision in terms of measuring the dependent variable. Another strength is the precise calculation of the slope and y-intercept uncertainties allowing for full comprehension of the true value of both quantities’ true values for each wavelength.

Limitations:

<u>Limitation</u>	<u>Improvement upon limitation</u>
The incrementing of the voltage a total of 5 times per wavelength.	The voltage can be incremented more times per wavelength allowing for a more representative curve and perhaps increased linearity.
The assumption of temperature (300 kelvin)	This limitation can be resolved by utilizing a more comprehensive simulation which accounts for temperature and its effects in a circuit.

Extension:

- 1- Using the calculated η as well as I_s values, the Shockley diode equation can be tailored ex. Ultra-Red; $I = (1.28074 * 10^{(-11)}) (e^{\frac{(1.6 * 10^{(-19)})V}{(3.05271272)(1.38 * 10^{(-23)})(300)}})$ varying v (at more spread increments) thus generating error-free current readings. Subsequently the natural log of I can be taken and plotted against V, allowing for a more linear relationship and a R-squared value 1. The illustrated process may be repeated for all wavelengths.
- 2- Measuring the influence of temperature on current using the Shockley diode equation.

Bibliography

- Jones, M. (2014). Test Equipment Principles. In *Building Valve Amplifiers (Second Edition)* (pp. 235-380). Newnes.
- Banerjee, D., & Chattopadhyay, K. K. (2018). A Low-Cost-Efficient Optoelectronic Material: Light-Emitting Diodes. In *Hybrid Inorganic Organic Perovskites* (pp. 123-162). ACADEMIC PRESS.
- Unacademy. (n.d.). *I-V Characteristics of LED*. Retrieved from Unacademy: <https://unacademy.com/content/jee/study-material/physics/i-v-characteristics-of-led/>
- PVEducation. (n.d.). *Diode Equation*. Retrieved from pveducation.org: <https://www.pveducation.org/pvcdrom/pn-junctions/diode-equation>
- Shockley, W. (1949). The Theory of p-n Junctions in Semiconductors and p-n Junction Transistors. . *Bell System Technical Journal*, 435-489.
- PVEducation. (n.d.). *Measuring Ideality Factor*. Retrieved from pveducation.org: <https://www.pveducation.org/pvcdrom/characterisation/measuring-ideality-factor>
- Engineering LibreTexts. (2021, July 6). *Ideal Diode Equation*. Retrieved from Engineering LibreTexts: [https://eng.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Materials_Science/Supplemental_Modules_\(Materials_Science\)/Solar_Basics/D._P-N_Junction_Diodes/3%3A_Ideal_Diode_Equation](https://eng.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Materials_Science/Supplemental_Modules_(Materials_Science)/Solar_Basics/D._P-N_Junction_Diodes/3%3A_Ideal_Diode_Equation)
- The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica. (1998, July 20). *diode*. Retrieved from Britannica: <https://www.britannica.com/technology/diode>
- Zarrintaj, P., Vahabi, H., Saeb, M., & Masous, M. (2019). Fundamentals and Emerging Applications of Polyaniline. In *Chapter 14 - Application of polyaniline and its derivatives 1.3 Electroluminescence devices* (pp. 259-272). Elsevier.
- Electrical4U. (2021, April 11). *Diode: Definition, Symbol, and Types of Diodes*. Retrieved from Electrical 4 U: <https://www.electrical4u.com/diode-working-principle-and-types-of-diode/>
- Electronics Tutorials. (2020). *The Light Emitting Diode*. Retrieved from ElectronicsTutorials: https://www.electronics-tutorials.ws/diode/diode_8.html
- BYJU'S. (2020). *p-n Junction- Definition, Formation, Application, VI Characteristics*. Retrieved from BYJU'S: <https://byjus.com/physics/p-n-junction/>
- DCACLAB. (2018, April 18). *UPDATES FOR LED IN DCACLAB*. Retrieved from DCACLAB: <https://dcaclab.com/blog/updates-for-led-in-dcaclab/>
- Tsokos, K. (2014). *Physics for the IB Diploma Sixth Edition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Appendix 1: LED Color wavelengths

	Wavelength (nm)	Color Name	Fwd Voltage (Vf @ 20ma)	Intensity 5mm LEDs	Viewing Angle	LED Dye Material
	940	Infrared	1.5	16mW @50mA	15°	GaAIAs/GaAs -- Gallium Aluminum Arsenide/Gallium Arsenide
	880	Infrared	1.7	18mW @50mA	15°	GaAIAs/GaAs -- Gallium Aluminum Arsenide/Gallium Arsenide
	850	Infrared	1.7	26mW @50mA	15°	GaAIAs/GaAs -- Gallium Aluminum Arsenide/Gallium Aluminum Arsenide
	660	Ultra Red	1.8	2000mcd @50mA	15°	GaAIAs/GaAs -- Gallium Aluminum Arsenide/Gallium Aluminum Arsenide
	635	High Eff. Red	2.0	200mcd @20mA	15°	GaAsP/GaP - Gallium Arsenic Phosphide / Gallium Phosphide
	633	Super Red	2.2	3500mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	620	Super Orange	2.2	4500mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	612	Super Orange	2.2	6500mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	605	Orange	2.1	160mcd @20mA	15°	GaAsP/GaP - Gallium Arsenic Phosphide / Gallium Phosphide
	595	Super Yellow	2.2	5500mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	592	Super Pure Yellow	2.1	7000mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	585	Yellow	2.1	100mcd @20mA	15°	GaAsP/GaP - Gallium Arsenic Phosphide / Gallium Phosphide
	4500K	"Incandescent" White	3.6	2000mcd @20mA	20°	SiC/GaN -- Silicon Carbide/Gallium Nitride
	6500K	Pale White	3.6	4000mcd @20mA	20°	SiC/GaN -- Silicon Carbide/Gallium Nitride
	8000K	Cool White	3.6	6000mcd @20mA	20°	SiC/GaN - Silicon Carbide / Gallium Nitride
	574	Super Lime Yellow	2.4	1000mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	570	Super Lime Green	2.0	1000mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	565	High Efficiency Green	2.1	200mcd @20mA	15°	GaP/GaP - Gallium Phosphide/Gallium Phosphide
	560	Super Pure Green	2.1	350mcd @20mA	15°	InGaAlP - Indium Gallium Aluminum Phosphide
	555	Pure Green	2.1	80mcd @20mA	15°	GaP/GaP - Gallium Phosphide/ Gallium Phosphide
	525	Aqua Green	3.5	10,000mcd @20mA	15°	SiC/GaN - Silicon Carbide / Gallium Nitride
	505	Blue Green	3.5	2000mcd @20mA	45°	SiC/GaN - Silicon Carbide / Gallium Nitride
	470	Super Blue	3.6	3000mcd @20mA	15°	SiC/GaN - Silicon Carbide / Gallium Nitride
	430	Ultra Blue	3.8	100mcd @20mA	15°	SiC/GaN - Silicon Carbide / Gallium Nitride

Appendix 2: Complete processed data

Color/ λ (nm)	Current (A) ± 0.00001	ln(I) (A)
Ultra-red - 660	0.00013	-8.9479761
	0.00072	-7.2362593
	0.00327	-5.7229653
	0.00975	-4.6304880
	0.01982	-3.9210638
Super Orange - 612	0.00062	-7.3857911
	0.00232	-6.0661881
	0.00679	-4.9923043
	0.01468	-4.2212693
	0.02520	-3.6809113
Yellow - 585	0.00045	-7.7062630
	0.00182	-6.3089188
	0.00584	-5.1430245
	0.01345	-4.3087762
	0.02388	-3.7347140
Super lime green - 570	0.00031	-8.0789383
	0.00139	-6.5784515
	0.00493	-5.3124163
	0.01222	-4.4046813
	0.02255	-3.7920202
Aqua green - 525	0.00146	-6.5293188
	0.00310	-5.7763532
	0.00685	-4.9835066
	0.01225	-4.4022293
	0.02402	-3.7288685
Super blue - 470	0.00173	-6.3596339
	0.00379	-5.5753893
	0.00757	-4.8835622
	0.01348	-4.3065482
	0.02148	-3.8406330
Ultra-blue - 430	0.00234	-6.0576043
	0.00482	-5.3349814
	0.00907	-4.7027830
	0.01537	-4.1753377
	0.02360	-3.7465086